

From Real Contexts to Fraction Understanding: Implementing Realistic Mathematics Education Using Visual Models and Number Lines

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 16 January 2026</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Risna Amelia</p>	<p>Mathematics is a subject that plays an important role in developing students' logical, critical, and systematic thinking skills. However, in reality, many junior high school students still have difficulty understanding abstract mathematical concepts, one of which is fractions. This difficulty often arises because students understand fractions procedurally without adequate conceptual understanding. The Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) approach is considered relevant because it links mathematics learning to real contexts that are close to students' lives. This study aims to describe the learning trajectory of junior high school students in understanding the concept of fractions through the application of the RME approach. The research used a descriptive qualitative method with a case study approach. The research subjects consisted of three seventh-grade students from SMP Negeri 2 Depok who were selected using purposive sampling. The learning was carried out in two meetings with real contexts, such as pizza sharing, juice consumption, and study schedules. Data were collected through direct observation and documentation of students' work, then analyzed using qualitative data analysis techniques, including data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results of the study indicate that the application of the RME approach can facilitate the gradual understanding of fractions, from concrete experiences to abstract understanding. There were variations in learning paths among students, where some students were able to abstract directly, while others needed visual models to overcome misconceptions. These findings indicate that the RME approach is effective in helping students build a more meaningful understanding of fractions.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Realistic Mathematics Education; Fractions; Real-World Contexts; Learning Pathways.</p>	

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is one of the subjects that plays an important role in developing logical, critical, and systematic thinking skills. Mathematics plays a very important role in various aspects of human life, as it improves logical, critical, systematic, and problem-solving thinking skills (Anggraini et al., 2023). This is in line with what Hariri & Kania (2025) explained, that mathematics plays an important role in fostering students' logical, critical, and analytical thinking skills. However, in reality, many students still experience difficulties in learning abstract mathematical concepts, as shown in the study by Klorina & Prabawanto (2023), which indicates that many students still have difficulty understanding abstract mathematical concepts, especially in the form of algebra. In addition, research by Yonathan & Selek (2023) also states that many students have difficulty

understanding abstract mathematical concepts, as evidenced during classroom observations where students faced difficulties with trigonometry and problem solving.

The ability to understand abstract mathematical concepts is closely related to students' abstraction skills, which are an extension of their prior knowledge from elementary school (Sun & Yang, 2023). At the junior high school level, the demands for understanding mathematical concepts become more complex, requiring students to have the ability to relate concrete experiences to more formal and abstract mathematical representations.

One learning approach that can help students understand abstract mathematical concepts is the reality-based learning approach. Jatiariska et al. (2022) state that the realistic mathematics approach helps students understand abstract concepts by utilizing contextual problems and

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models. This approach encourages students to connect mathematical ideas with real-life situations, improving their understanding and visualization of problems.

The Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) learning theory was developed in the Netherlands in the 1970s by Hans Freudenthal based on the view that mathematics is a human activity. In this approach, learning begins with real contexts that are familiar to students, then develops through models, and finally reaches abstract formal symbols. In line with Mashuri (2023), who explains that this approach begins learning from real contexts that are familiar to students' lives, using real-world problems as a starting point. Students then develop their understanding through models and discussions before reaching more abstract formal symbols.

The learning process in RME involves two types of mathematization, namely horizontal and vertical mathematization. Horizontal mathematization focuses on the process of converting real-life problems into mathematical representations so that they can be processed mathematically. In contrast, vertical mathematization focuses on processing these representations to a more abstract level through mathematical reasoning and structures (Charlo, 2020). According to de Lange (1987: 72), the Indonesian Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) learning process can be described as follows:

Figure 1 PMRI Learning Process

The RME (Realistic Mathematics Education) approach emphasizes connecting mathematics with real-life situations, which helps students understand abstract mathematical concepts (Samura & Siagian 2023). Realistic in RME does not only mean that student learning is linked to facts or reality, but also means that students are brought to problems of facts or reality that occur in everyday life. The process of solving realistic problems can be described as follows:

Figure 2 Realistic Problem Solving

Several studies have shown the effectiveness of the RME approach in mathematics learning. Koerunnisa et al. (2025) stated that the Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) approach effectively bridges the gap between abstract mathematical concepts and practical applications by using real-world problems. In addition, Gee (2019) research also explains that there is an increase in problem-solving skills, which before using the RME-based learning flow were in the very poor category with an average score of 48.41. Meanwhile, after using the RME-based learning flow on the topics of sequences and series, the data obtained on students' mathematical problem-solving abilities was in the good category, as indicated by an average score of 74.85.

At the junior high school level, the concept of fractions is an important foundation for understanding advanced mathematical material such as decimals, percentages, ratios, and algebra. Therefore, conceptual understanding of fractions not only affects learning success in this material, but also determines students' readiness to learn subsequent mathematical concepts. When students experience misconceptions about fractions, these difficulties tend to carry over and develop in subsequent material. This shows that fraction learning needs to be designed meaningfully by paying attention to the thinking process and how students construct understanding, not just the achievement of final results. Fractions are often only understood by students as mechanical procedures, such as equalizing denominators or using addition formulas, without understanding the meaning of fractions as part of a whole. Research by Lee & Boyadzhiev (2020) found that students often have misconceptions about fractions, such as misunderstandings of basic definitions, the least common denominator, and the order of operations.

This lack of conceptual understanding leads to errors because students may remember the procedure but fail to calculate fractions accurately. This is in line with research by Altıparmak & Ozidogru (2015), which reveals that students often view fractions through limited mechanical procedures, such as equalizing denominators or applying addition formulas, without understanding the underlying concept of fractions as a part-whole relationship. This misunderstanding hinders students' understanding of advanced material such as decimals, percentages, and ratios.

Based on a literature review, research that specifically examines students' learning trajectories in understanding fractions through the Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) approach is still very limited. Most previous studies have focused more on improving learning outcomes or specific abilities, rather than on the variations in learning trajectories taken by students when using Realistic Mathematics Education (RME). In fact, understanding learning trajectories is very important for teachers to know the differences in how students construct knowledge. Kohar et al (2021) explain that understanding learning trajectories through the RME approach is very important for teachers

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because it highlights how students construct knowledge differently.

Based on the above description, this study was conducted as a case study with the aim of describing junior high school students' learning trajectories in understanding fractions through the application of Realistic Mathematics Education (RME). This study is expected to contribute to the development of more contextual mathematics learning strategies, in line with the direction of the Merdeka Curriculum, and to provide new insights into the variations in students' learning trajectories in constructing the concept of fractions.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a descriptive qualitative method with a case study approach. The focus of the study is learning fractions through real contexts and developing fraction operations by applying the Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) approach.

Table 1 Data Collection Details

Day, Date	Meeting	Materi
Wednesday, 4 June 2025	1	Understanding fractions through real-world contexts
Thursday, 5 June 2025	2	Development of fractional operations

C. Data Collection Instruments and Techniques

The main instrument used in this study was a format for documenting student work. This instrument was developed based on RME approach indicators and met the principles of validity and clarity of content.

Table 2 Data Collection Techniques

Data Collection Techniques	Explanation
Direct observation	Observing the learning process in the classroom.
Documentation	Collect data in the form of student work (activity sheets, model drawings, notes), photos of activities, and field notes.

D. Data Analysis Techniques

The data obtained from observation and documentation was analyzed using qualitative data analysis techniques. The analysis process was carried out in three stages, namely data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. These stages aimed to obtain a clear picture of the students' learning trajectory in understanding fractions through the RME approach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study implemented the Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) approach on three seventh-grade students to explore the process of forming an understanding of fractions during learning. The findings in this study indicate that students' understanding of fractions was formed through

A. Research Design

The research stages were designed operationally based on the principles of Realistic Mathematics Education (RME). The learning process began with the introduction of real contexts close to the students' lives, followed by the use of concrete models in the form of visual media. Next, students engage in discussion and reflection activities to construct their understanding. The final stage of learning is directed at the process of concept generalization through horizontal and vertical mathematization, so that students can move from concrete experiences to a more abstract understanding of fractions.

B. Subject, Location, and Time of Research

The research subjects consisted of three seventh-grade students selected using purposive sampling techniques, taking into account the students' varying abilities in understanding fractions. This study was conducted at SMP Negeri 2 Depok. Data collection was carried out in the even semester of the 2024/2025 academic year, divided into two meetings as shown in the following table:

The data collection techniques used in this study included direct observation and documentation, as presented in the following table:

active involvement in the learning process, students' responses to the contextual problems presented, and the results of students' work during learning activities. Through this series of activities, students interpreted the meaning of fractions based on experiences close to their daily lives.

The research findings also highlight the relationship between student learning activities and the characteristics of the RME approach. The context of the problems used encouraged students to start thinking intuitively, then develop their understanding through the use of models as representations of fractions. Furthermore, students' contributions in expressing strategies and reasons, as well as the interactions that occur through discussion, help students clarify and deepen their understanding of the concept. This process shows that context, models, and interactions play an

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important role in helping students build their understanding of fractions gradually, from contextual understanding to a more mathematical understanding.

The learning was conducted in two sessions, each of which showed the development of students' understanding. The discussion of the findings was presented based on the RME syntax, namely understanding the context of the problem, exploring models, student contributions, interactions, and reflections, to describe how each stage of learning contributed to the process of understanding fractions as demonstrated by the students.

A. Learning Implementation and Findings in the Field

Meeting 1: Understanding fractions through real contexts

The lesson began by presenting a contextual problem in the form of dividing a pizza, then showing a picture of the pizza and asking:

“If we divide the pizza into 4 pieces, how many pieces will we get?”.

Students were asked to describe the situation in their own way. The goal was for students to understand that fractions are parts of a whole.

The results of the students' work showed a variety of visual representations. Student A was able to divide proportionally, Student B used visual aids but had difficulty with complex divisions, while Student C showed hesitation and fixation on symbols. For more details, see the following table:

Table 3 Understanding Fractions Through Real-Life Contexts

No.	Student Code	Contextual Representation	Ability to Express Fractions	Level of Understanding
1.	S-A	Divide the pizza image into 2, 4, and 8 equal parts proportionally.	Accurate (Able to explain the relationship between the denominator and the size of the part)	High
2.	S-B	Able to divide by 2, but has difficulty visually dividing into 8 parts ($\frac{3}{8}$)	Enough (Initially confused, understood after discussion)	Medium
3.	S-C	Hesitant in dividing the circle: assuming $\frac{2}{4} \neq \frac{1}{2}$	It is not appropriate to focus on numerical symbols.	Low

Based on Table 3, Student A has correctly understood the concept of “part of a whole.” Student C's mistake shows that symbolic understanding has not yet been fully formed. The learning process then continued with a class discussion. Student C showed new understanding after the teacher linked the context to the experience of dividing objects fairly.

These results show that concrete contexts help students construct the meaning of fractions from everyday

experiences, in accordance with the PMR principle that learning mathematics must begin with realities that are meaningful to students

Meeting 2: Development of Fraction Operations.

The second session was designed to continue the previous activities toward an understanding of addition and subtraction operations with fractions.

Table 4 Development of Fractional Operations

No.	Student Code	Initial Response to the Operation ($\frac{2}{4} + \frac{1}{2}$)	Observed Cognitive Processes
1.	S-A	Perform symbolic conversion immediately	Vertical Mathematization: Has reached the abstraction stage (model for)
2.	S-B	Using circle images to see similarities in area	Intertwin: Connecting visuals with symbols; transition phase.
3.	S-C	Misconception ($\frac{2}{4} + \frac{1}{2} = \frac{2}{6}$), then corrected with an illustration.	Guided Reinvention: Misconceptions are overcome through visual aids.

Overall, the second meeting successfully facilitated understanding of fraction operations. The models constructed by students (such as pizza pictures and number lines) began

to develop into thinking tools that could be used to generalize concepts without having to rely entirely on the initial context.

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The following is an in-depth description of the students' learning trajectories for each problem given:

Problem 1: Pizza Context (Addition of Equivalent Fractions).

Lina memiliki $\frac{1}{2}$ bagian pizza, lalu temannya memberikan $\frac{1}{4}$ bagian pizza lagi.

Real World Situation

Berapa bagian pizza yang dimiliki Lina sekarang?

Jawaban:

$$\textcircled{1} \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} = \frac{2}{4} + \frac{1}{4} = \frac{3}{4}$$

Formal Knowledge

Figure 3 Answer S-A to Problem 1

Student A solved the problem symbolically without using pictures. He immediately wrote $\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} = \frac{2}{4} + \frac{1}{4} = \frac{3}{4}$. The strategy used shows that student A was at the stage of vertical mathematization, where understanding no longer depended on concrete models.

Model For

Formal Knowledge

Figure 4 Answer S-B to Problem 1

Unlike student A, student B immediately used visual representation as a first step. He drew two circles and concluded that $\frac{1}{2}$ was equal to $\frac{2}{4}$. This strategy reflects an intertwined process, namely the interconnection between visual models and symbolic notation.

$$\textcircled{1} \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} = \frac{2}{4}$$

Model For

$$\frac{1}{2} = \frac{2}{4}$$

$$\frac{2}{4} + \frac{1}{4} = \frac{3}{4}$$

Formal Knowledge

Formal Knowledge

Figure 5 Answer S-C to Problem 1

Student C began solving the problem with an incorrect answer ($\frac{2}{6}$). However, after drawing a visualization, Student C realized that $\frac{1}{2}$ could be changed to $\frac{2}{4}$ and corrected their answer.

This thought process illustrates the guided reinvention stage in the RME approach.

Problem 2: Context Orange Juice (Different Referent)

Putra minum $\frac{5}{12}$ liter jus jeruk saat sarapan dan $\frac{1}{4}$ liter lagi saat makan siang.

Real World Situation

Berapa liter jus yang telah diminum Putra secara keseluruhan?

$$\textcircled{2} \frac{5}{12} + \frac{1}{4} = \frac{5}{12} + \frac{3}{12} = \frac{8}{12} = \frac{2}{3}$$

Formal Knowledge

Figure 6 Answer S-A to Problem 2

Student A uses a symbolic strategy, converting $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{3}{12}$, then adding and simplifying the result to $\frac{2}{3}$. This illustrates an effort to use an algorithmic strategy, although it still requires strengthening of symbolic understanding.

Model Of

Formal Knowledge

Figure 7 Answer S-B to Problem 2

Student B uses a visual representation of two number lines to convert $\frac{1}{4}$ into $\frac{3}{12}$ visually. This shows that students are at the horizontal mathematization stage, where concrete context models are used to represent problems.

$$\textcircled{2} \frac{5}{12} + \frac{1}{4} = \frac{8}{12}$$

Formal Knowledge

Model Of

Formal Knowledge

Figure 8 Answer S-C to Problem 2

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Student C initially made a mistake $\frac{6}{16}$ but switched to using a visual strategy (bar model) to correct the answer to $\frac{8}{12}$. This approach demonstrates a process of reflection and strategy refinement by the student.

Problem 3: Context of the learning schedule (Addition and simplification)

Ali memiliki jadwal belajar harian yang ia atur sendiri di rumah. Pada pagi hari, setelah sarapan, ia belajar mata pelajaran Matematika selama $\frac{1}{3}$ jam. Kemudian setelah bermain dan istirahat siang, Ali kembali membuka bukunya dan belajar kembali selama $\frac{1}{6}$ jam di sore hari.

Real World Situation

Jika seluruh waktu belajar Ali dalam satu hari hanya terdiri dari dua sesi tersebut. berapa jam total waktu yang digunakan Ali untuk belajar pada hari itu?

Formal Knowledge

Figure 9 Answer S-A to Problem 3

Student A solved the problem symbolically. She immediately equalized the denominators and simplified the result to $\frac{1}{2}$ hours. This result demonstrates a strong understanding of the procedure without visual aids.

Formal Knowledge

Figure 10 Answer S-B to Problem 3

Student B uses a visual representation in the form of two number lines to show that $\frac{1}{3} = \frac{2}{6}$ and then adds them together. This visual aid is very helpful in understanding the concept of equivalent fractions.

Formal Knowledge

Model Of

Formal Knowledge

Figure 11 Answer S-C to Problem 3

Student C initially made a mistake ($\frac{2}{9}$), but corrected his answer using visual strategies. This reinforces that contextual and visual approaches are very useful in developing students' conceptual understanding.

The findings regarding the variations in the learning trajectories of the three students confirm that the construction of mathematical knowledge is dynamic and unique to each individual. Student C's success in self-correction through visual aids, as well as Student A's fluency in abstracting concepts, show that the use of diverse contexts, ranging from concrete objects such as pizza to abstract situations such as study schedules, can facilitate a wide spectrum of student abilities. Student interaction with visual models has been proven to be not merely a calculation aid, but a valid cognitive bridge for remedying procedural misconceptions that often occur in fraction operations.

However, the dynamics captured in the case study of this small group represent the diversity that may arise in larger classes, which certainly requires teachers to be sensitive in facilitating differentiated learning. Hidayati, (2020) explains that diversity in larger classes can be realized through various student readiness, interests, and learning profiles, which require teachers to be sensitive in facilitating different teaching methods. Thus, teachers are required to recognize and adapt learning strategies adaptively.

The transition from concrete to abstract understanding observed in these two meetings is a positive early indicator of the RME approach, but the consolidation of intertwined concepts and emergent modeling should ideally be built through a continuous learning process to ensure optimal and in-depth knowledge retention. Pickhardt et al., (2022) explain that by integrating modeling and visualization competencies, students can effectively transition between different educational contexts, thereby improving their ability to apply mathematical concepts in real-world scenarios, which is essential for optimal knowledge retention.

The results of this study are in line with the Iceberg theory in RME proposed by Gravemeijer (1994 : 92) that in a realistic approach, emphasis is placed on mathematization. Mathematics is viewed as a human activity, so learning mathematics means doing mathematics. Solving everyday

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problems is an essential part of learning, where various contextual problems are integrated from the outset. Abstract knowledge does not stand alone but must be adapted to solve real-life problems, while real-life problems must be translated into formal mathematical forms.

Figure 12 Application of formal mathematics

This view is also in line with Freudenthal (1991), who states that effective learning moves from the situational level to the formal level. This process is illustrated through the iceberg model in fraction learning:

Figure 13 Fraction Learning Iceberg

Students' understanding develops gradually from concrete experiences to abstract mathematical concepts. In addition, through the processes of horizontal and vertical mathematization, students are guided to build their understanding of concepts gradually. Horizontal mathematization helps students transform contextual problems into mathematical representations, while vertical mathematization allows students to develop these representations into more formal and organized mathematical structures. Gravemeijer (1994 : 93) emphasizes that vertical mathematization plays an important role in developing reasoning and generalization of mathematical concepts, as shown in the following figure

Figure 14 Vertical Mathematizing

The findings of this study are also in line with several previous studies that show that the realistic mathematics education (RME) approach is effective in improving students' understanding of mathematical concepts through the use of real contexts. The research by Agustina et al. (2025) shows that RME encourages active student engagement and helps the transition from concrete to abstract understanding in a more systematic way. Similar findings were also reported by Utami et al. (2022), who concluded that RME learning aided by contextual media is significantly more effective than conventional learning in building students' understanding of mathematical concepts.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that the implementation of the Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) approach is effective in bridging students' understanding from real experiences to abstract concepts of fractions. The research findings show variations in students' learning paths and responses. Students with stronger conceptual understanding are able to directly relate mathematical ideas through concrete models, while students who still experience uncertainty require additional visual support and guidance to understand basic concepts, especially the difference between numerators and denominators. The RME approach provides space for students to learn actively through contextual experiences, the use of models, and discussions, thereby supporting the formation of a deeper conceptual understanding.

Based on these conclusions, it is recommended that fraction learning in seventh grade junior high school optimize the use of concrete and visual models, such as real objects (e.g., pizza), to provide a clearer and more understandable representation of the concept to students. Teachers are also recommended to extend the duration and quality of group discussions so that students have greater opportunities to exchange ideas and build understanding collaboratively. In addition, intensive scaffolding is necessary to help students

understand essential concepts, such as the difference between numerators and denominators and the equivalence of fractions. Learning evaluation should be carried out continuously through observation and systematic feedback to comprehensively monitor students' progress in understanding.

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